

E-COMMERCE WEB APPLICATION FOR THE TOGO FOOTWEAR STORE

Sasini Prathibha¹, Champa Hewagamage², Kavinga Elamulla³

Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura

[1sasiniprathiba3@gmail.com](mailto:sasiniprathiba3@gmail.com), [2champah@sjp.ac.lk](mailto:champah@sjp.ac.lk), [3kpkavinga@gmail.com](mailto:kpkavinga@gmail.com)

Background

Organization and Business Domain

The TOGO Footwear Store falls within the SME scale business category. This company was established in 2018. Initially, there were no staff, and he made shoes and sold them locally in his own home, keeping cash transaction books and recording transaction details. At the moment, an outlet has been opened in Lunugamwehera, the town nearest to it, employing numerous employees, and shoes are sold both In-store and online (through Facebook pages, Instagram, and WhatsApp). Throughout the transaction, sales information is entered using a computer.

Overview of the Existing System

How the existing system functions:

At the moment, TOGO Footwear Store operate his business manually and this store sells shoes both in-store and through various Facebook pages, Instagram, etc. without using any technology, software, web applications, or other solutions. Sales and transaction information is entered manually into a computer. All of the entered data is recorded in a manual book at the end of each month.

Problems with the existing System:

Several problems were encountered manual selling system. That is, although they use several Facebook pages for their selling activities, their

marketing efforts are not very effective. The reasons were customers' dissatisfaction, and their less profitability than they expected, taking more time to maintain handwritten records than utilizing a computerized system, and having more data as they used to maintain the transaction details on papers, which raises the cost.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

More consideration must be given to the technical aspects of the business environment if one is to successfully navigate the evolving, competitive business world today. The utilization of technical aspects thus decreased the issues in the TOGO Footwear Store. In order to earn greater revenues both locally and globally in a business environment that is competitive, to build an enterprise of the highest quality that offers the best strategic competition, a solution is required. Eventually, it was proposed that this company required an e-commerce web application.

Requirement Analysis

Basically, in an e-commerce web application, **Functional Requirements** and **Non-Functional Requirements** (Security, Usability, Availability, Performance) were defined. Below main functional requirements were identified in relation to the system's inputs, processes, outputs, and database activities that are necessary to meet the needs of the users.

- Both registered and unregistered users may create accounts and log in to their accounts using the proper username and password.
- The consumer can choose the shoes they desire or place an order using the application's special "Order to Design" feature.
- Customers can evaluate their shopping cart items and add shoes.
- Customers can make payments online using their bank card information (Exp year, month, and CVC).

Proposed System and Objectives

We suggested implementing an e-commerce web application with four key modules to address the problems of the TOGO Footwear Store was experiencing. Those modules are,

- ✓ **Customer Management** (Create an account, Login, Select the shoes, add to cart, Order to design, Request order, Cancel the order)
- ✓ **Payment Management** (Choose the customer bank, enter bank card details, submit card details, Receive message (Successfully))
- ✓ **Delivery Management** (Send delivery message to customer, select customer address, Dispatch the order to Currier service)
- ✓ **Inventory Management** (Update the product stock using Barcode, Set the re-order level, show re-order level through notification, Create the stock order request)

Following objectives are expected to be achieved through the proposed e-commerce web application.

1. Customers can customize shoes to fit their demands.
2. Allow customers to pay online.
3. The TOGO Footwear Store's commercial operations can be carried out efficiently.

System Development

Development Methodology used

E-commerce system development is conducted using the agile methodology. A web application project for e-commerce benefits greatly from the use of agile methodology. Utilizing the agile method has several benefits.

Technologies used

- Backend development Language: PHP
- Frontend development: HTML, CSS, JavaScript
- Database Management system: MySQL database
- IDE: Visual Studio Code
- Web server: Apache web server

Conclusion

Main objectives of the system were achieved by e-commerce web application for the TOGO Footwear Store. Only two modules of this project have been developed, such as Customer management and Payment Management Modules. The system can be improved further to provide greater facilities to assist the users, and those enhancements will also raise the degree of user satisfaction.

References

BluEnt. (n.d.). Retrieved from Why Agile Methodology Is Perfect For the eCommerce Industry: <https://www.bluent.net/blog/why-agile-methodology-is-perfect-for-the-ecommerce-industry/>